

ETHICAL AND LEGAL CHALLENGES OF AI CREATIVITY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has led to increased accessibility and ease of use in creative applications, while simultaneously raising ethical and legal challenges. This systematic review aims to explore the consequences of premature adoption of unbridled AI technology, particularly in the context of AI-generated creative content. The study focuses on the ethical dilemmas and risks associated with AI creativity, such as questions of authorship, ownership, and originality. This study is an effort to ascertain the creative aspects of machine as well as human mind by analyzing ethical and legal challenges and prospects of AI through the systematic literature review using PRISMA Model Using the PRISMA model, a comprehensive literature review is conducted to analyze the need for responsive and adaptive policies that ensure ethical measures in the face of challenges posed by AI in the media landscape. Systematic literature review helps in minimizing biasness and maximizing the contribution of empirical studies in stated field. The review also examines the potential risks to intellectual property rights and the necessity for concrete safeguards. The study aims to contribute to the understanding of how AI-generated creations can be connected to formulate ethical and legal frameworks, benefiting society in the application of innovative technologies. The insights gained from this research provides a foundation for stakeholders to develop measures that protect creativity, novelty, and uniqueness in the era of technological advancement.

INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement

This study investigates the ethical dilemmas and challenges associated with AI creativity. As noted by Dr. Tayyab Shah, AI is akin to "driverless technology," and its premature adoption has accelerated numerous ethical and legal challenges for individuals and the public domain due to its unregulated nature. These

concerns have raised questions among stakeholders regarding the authenticity of AI-generated content in two distinct ways. On one hand, there is concern about the generative content produced from user inputs, while on the other, there is significant apprehension among entities or companies whose databases are utilized without permission or licenses

for training data in AI generator programs. These issues, among others, necessitate an expedited philosophical debate on the matter. This study aims to explore more appropriate methods to identify creative aspects by analyzing the ethical challenges and prospects of AI-generated creations through a systematic literature review. The intention is to contribute to the understanding of how AI-generated creations can be integrated to formulate responsive and adaptive measures, ensuring a more ethical and legal approach to the challenges posed by evolving media landscapes. By staying at the forefront of advancements in media and technology, this study also aims to benefit society by applying innovative technologies to creative, ethical, and legal frameworks. It provides a foundation for an examination of AI creativity, which is considered one of the most significant ethically and legally complex issues in contemporary communication progress.

Research Objectives

To explore the ethical implications of AI-generated creative content and propose guidelines for responsible implementation.

To investigate the legal frameworks necessary to protect intellectual property rights in an era of AI-driven content creation.

To develop a set of best practices for integrating GAI technologies into existing media production workflows while maintaining artistic integrity and originality.

Research Questions

Q1: What ethical and legal challenges are being faced as consequential result of pre-mature adoption of AI Technology?

Q2: How responsive and adoptive policies, ensuring ethical remedial measures to the challenges posed by AI in media landscape?

Introduction

Evolution of Artificial Intelligence

In 1920, the word "robot" first appeared in modern literature in the play R.U.R. Rossum's Universal Robots by Czech writer Karel Čapek (Raj & Kos, 2022). In Czech, "robot" means forced labor. The play introduced the idea of "singularity," where smart machines become more advanced than humans and

stop being just workers. In 1927, Fritz Lang's film Metropolis explored similar ideas (J. Garon, 2023). Isaac Asimov made robots and artificial intelligence more popular. He wrote over 36 books about self-aware robots and many stories about "Multivac," a big government machine that could understand questions and give smart answers (J. M. Garon, 2023).

Fictional portrayals frequently shape the common understanding of the rise of these technologies. The term "artificial intelligence" was first introduced by John McCarthy at a 1956 conference at Dartmouth College, which focused on replicating human-like cognitive processes in computers (Roitblat, 2020). While efforts to replicate human thought and decision-making have been ongoing for many years, the last five years have witnessed a significant surge in AI implementation. AI is now a driving force behind major technological advancements, including experiments with autonomous vehicles, healthcare innovations, facial recognition for unlocking phones, and applications in music production, digital imagery, deepfake videos, and more (J. M. Garon, 2023). The academic roots of AI as a discipline can be traced back to 1956. Research in AI encompasses cognition, insight, rationality, wisdom, demonstration, development, natural language processing, and the ability to move independently and manipulate objects (Raj & Kos, 2022). In the esteemed journal "Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach" by Russell and Norvig, AI is described as "the study of agents that receive awareness from the environment and execute actions." This definition simplifies actions to their mechanical outcomes, without specifying their objectives (the goals the agent pursues or, philosophically speaking, intentions). These goals are externally provided, suggesting that artificial agents do not initiate actions on their own and lack awareness of their actions when they perform them (Powers & Ganascia, 2020).

Literature Review

Writers have long been intrigued by the progress of technology and its relationship with humans (Nils J Nilsson, 2010). To grasp the core technologies of AI, one must first comprehend the notion of "Intelligence." Initially, intelligence can be described as "an agent's capacity to accomplish goals across different settings." Additionally, intelligence can be

understood as "the computational facet of the ability to achieve objectives in the world". In philosophical terms, an agent contemplates their actions before carrying them out, recognizing their intentions and acting accordingly. In essence, artificial agents lack agency from a philosophical standpoint (Ahmad & Gul, 2023a; Gul & Ahmad, 2023; Gul, Kanwal, & Khan, 2020)

Powers & Ganascia, 2020). AI (Artificial Intelligence) involves programming machines to replicate human intelligence in order to perform tasks (Mckinsy.com). The emergence of AI-generated content and AI-driven computer agents introduces new types of risks, the consequences of which are challenging to foresee. Technological progress has enabled the increasingly potent application of artificial intelligence, driven by vast amounts of digital content that can be utilized to examine users' behavior, mindset, and physical conditions (Lewis & Moorkens, 2020).

The ethical dilemmas associated with artificial intelligence (AI) are complex and increasingly urgent as AI technologies become more prevalent in fields such as healthcare, business, and education (Ahmad & Gul, 2023b; Gul & Ahmad, 2022a). The swift progress of AI demands a comprehensive evaluation of ethical frameworks to ensure these technologies are in harmony with societal values and human well-being (Zakir et al., 2025). This synthesis examines the current challenges and future prospects in AI ethics, referencing a variety of academic sources. The use of AI in medical decision-making has sparked concerns about the risk of misdiagnoses and disparities in treatment outcomes due to algorithmic bias (Weidener, 2024; Familoni, 2024; Olorunsogo, 2024). For example, Reddy et al. stress the importance of transparency and accountability in AI healthcare applications to reduce these risks (Reddy et al., 2019). Familoni further argues that ethical frameworks can enhance fairness and inclusiveness, thereby building trust among stakeholders (Familoni, 2024; Gul & Khan, 2020; Gul & Ahmad, 2022b). The pressing need to address these issues is highlighted by the growing dependence on AI for critical decisions, which can significantly impact patient welfare (Olorunsogo, 2024).

Furthermore, the absence of thorough ethical guidelines presents considerable obstacles for developers and practitioners. Many current

frameworks are criticized for being too theoretical and lacking practical solutions to the ethical challenges encountered in AI deployment (Gul & Reba, 2022; Khan, Gul, Riaz, Bibi, & Ahmad, 2025; Tufail, Gul, & Ali, 2024b; Mittelstadt, 2019; Cooreman, 2022). For instance, Mittelstadt contends that principles alone are insufficient to ensure ethical AI, advocating for a more nuanced approach to tackle the complexities of AI technologies (Mittelstadt, 2019). This view is supported by Khan et al., who point out a disconnect between ethical principles and their practical application, emphasizing the necessity for strong governance models to effectively address these issues (Khan et al., 2022).

Establishing global ethical standards for AI presents a significant chance to align efforts across different sectors and regions. Hoseini highlights that creating these standards is not merely a technical necessity but also a moral duty that requires collaboration from all stakeholders in AI development (Hoseini, 2023). This collaborative approach can facilitate the sharing of best practices and promote a more equitable distribution of AI benefits while mitigating the risks associated with its use (Olatoye, 2024). Furthermore, including diverse perspectives in the creation of these standards is essential to ensure that ethical considerations are both thorough and inclusive (Ali, Gul, & Gul, 2025; Bareach & Gul, 2025; Gul & Ali, 2021b; Gul & Khan, 2021; Hoseini, 2023). Beyond these challenges, the ethical dimensions of AI extend past technical issues to include wider societal concerns. The way AI ethics is portrayed in the media significantly influences public discussion and regulatory policies (Ouchchy et al., 2020) (Zakir et al., 2022). Analyzing how ethical matters are depicted in the media can offer insights into public perceptions and the potential consequences for AI governance (Ouchchy et al., 2020). Additionally, as AI continues to advance, educational systems must evolve to integrate ethical considerations, ensuring that future professionals are prepared to navigate the ethical complexities of AI technologies (Weidener, 2024; Tuomi, 2023).

One of the main issues in AI ethics is the widespread presence of bias and discrimination, especially in critical sectors like healthcare. New types of AI-generated content and AI-driven virtual agents introduce fresh risks, the consequences of which are

challenging to foresee (Lewis & Moorkens, 2020). The field of artificial intelligence (AI) ethics has developed in response to increasing worries about AI's impact (Gul & Khilji, 2021; Sohail, Gul, & Mushtaq, 2018; Tufail, Gul, & Ali, 2024a; Gul, Ilyas, Gul, Riaz, & Khan, 2025; Kazim & Koshiyama, 2021). AI has presented numerous challenges to the current legal framework of intellectual property rights, particularly concerning copyright law (Sandiumenge, 2023). There have been extensive discussions about the risks associated with the development and use of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI). This area includes issues like potential bias, privacy and security threats, ethical concerns, and the creation of harmful or misleading content (Zakir et al., 2025). Despite these concerns, Generative AI continues to be developed and applied in various contexts, leading to significant considerations of the societal and ethical consequences of these technologies ((Gul & Tahir, 2023a; Mehmood, Rao, & Gul, 2024; Gul, Rabbi, Batool, Tahir, & Asif, 2024b; Wach et al., 2023).

Recent developments have enabled Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) to produce content in various forms that often closely resembles human-created work, challenging the traditional belief that creativity is solely a human trait. The notion that creativity is an exclusive human domain is being questioned by the latest advancements in deep learning algorithms: generative AI (GAI) (Zakir et al., 2025). There are significant distinctions between the creative processes of humans and AI in all three components. Firstly, humans typically have access to a wide but shallow range of data, including life experiences and cultural and social contexts, many of which are inaccessible to AI due to their uncodified nature or regulatory limitations. Conversely, AI can tap into extensive but more focused datasets and represent them in high-dimensional spaces, surpassing the limitations of human cognitive capacity and memory by leveraging advancements in computing infrastructures and deep learning algorithms (Gul, Ayub, Mazhar, Uddin, & Khanum, 2021; Gul & Ali, 2021a; Gul & Dogar, 2021; He et al., 2023).

Programs and robots with intelligent capabilities are increasingly becoming part of our daily routines as assistants. At present, people utilize a variety of home appliances that incorporate smart technology and artificial intelligence, including automatic coffee

makers, vacuum cleaners, washing machines, smart TVs, and more. Personal assistant services like Siri and Alexa facilitate searching for information, controlling devices, and placing orders in smart homes. The integration of robotics and artificial intelligence provides researchers, scientists, and medical professionals with enhanced methods to boost the efficiency of their work (Raj & Kos, 2022). Most people agree that the essence of humanity is rooted in creativity and progress (Mammen & Richey, 2020). The Copyright Office has maintained the necessity of human authorship. As stated in Section 202.02(b) of the Compendium II of Copyright Office Practices, authorship must originate from a human to qualify for copyright protection. Works created solely by plants, animals, or natural phenomena are not eligible for copyright protection (Ayub, Gul, Ali, & Rauf, 2021; Bukhari, Gul, Bashir, Zakir, & Javed, 2021; Gul & Tahir, 2023b; Gul, Talat, Mumtaz, & Shaheen, 2021; Mammen & Richey, 2020).

Relying on copyright protection is an ineffective strategy for promoting the adoption and investment in AI technology. While machines excel in certain domains, they remain distinguishable from humans, particularly in creative endeavors. Algorithms lack essential human traits such as intention, awareness, emotions, motivation, and observation. Although artificial intelligence is achievable, artificial creativity is not (Zurth, 2020). The influence of technological progress on content creation using copyrighted materials necessitates adjustments in legal frameworks to align with new realities. There are varying approaches to copyright protection across different legal systems and cultures. A comprehensive strategy is deemed necessary to protect intellectual property rights, especially copyright laws, in the rapidly changing digital age (Gul, Rabbi, Batool, Tahir, & Asif, 2024a; Rabbi & Gul, 2023; Gul, et al., 2024; Zakir et al., 2025). Countries differ in their regulation of new types of works, with distinct laws governing databases and computer programs. The digital environment presents challenges for copyright protection, including difficulties in discerning legal from illegal activities. The impact of technology on copyright enforcement and the need for innovative business models to safeguard intellectual property are inevitable. It is crucial to strike a balance between private rights and the public interest in information,

which should be considered through research (Natalia Mogol Rodica Crudu, 2022).

The aim of investigating the copyright ramifications of generative artificial intelligence involves delving into topics like authorship, ownership, and infringement. The research focuses on exploring the legal challenges and considerations associated with this technology (Sandiumenge, 2023). In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has impacted nearly every facet of human creativity. AI has posed several challenges to the existing intellectual property legal framework, particularly in relation to copyright law (Torres, 2023). The achievements of artificial intelligence highlight the remarkable advancements in AI technologies over the past few decades, as well as the technology's swiftly growing influence and power within human society. The field of artificial intelligence is rapidly evolving, necessitating that policymakers and regulators remain informed about this emerging and vital technology (Villaronga, Kieseberg, & Li, 2018). The rise of AI-generated content and its application in literature and art have introduced new challenges for modern practices (Gaon, 2019).

The application of copyright laws concerning authorship, infringement, and fair use to content generated by artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming increasingly complex due to advancements in AI technology. Generative AI tools, such as DALL-E and ChatGPT from Open AI, Stable Diffusion from Stability AI, and the branding program from Midjourney, are capable of creating unique text, images, and other forms of content, or "results," in response to user-provided text prompts, commonly referred to as "inputs." These generative AI systems are trained to produce such outputs by being fed a vast array of existing works, including books, photographs, paintings, and other artistic creations. (Zirpoli, 2023) The challenges and intricacies related to copyright law in the context of AI-generated content are significant. The regulations concerning works produced by AI differ across countries. Traditionally, copyright law applies to original creations, emphasizing the author's distinct intellectual creativity and "personal touch," as highlighted in a landmark decision on copyright authorship (Zakir et al., 2025). It is clear that for a work to qualify for copyright protection, a human author is necessary, as the work must reflect the

author's individuality. The current basis of EU law is founded on the belief in the distinctiveness of human creativity and authorship. However, this human-focused perspective is being challenged by the emergence of creative tools. Particularly for works created with the "assistance" of AI technologies, the rise of AI is blurring the boundaries and complicating the legal definition of what constitutes a copyrightable work (Torres, 2023).

Methodology (Systematic Review Execution)

This research utilized the systematic literature review criteria to determine the questions under study. A systematic review criteria is adopted to get maximum utilization of previous researches in stated study for forming novel direction and reaching to concrete conclusions. A systematic review of several studies on Ethics of Artificial Intelligence examining the challenges and prospects can provide information that is empirically accurate and relevant to broad range of studies across different media platforms. It is considered the best, least biased and most rational way to organize, gather, evaluate and integrate scientific evidence from the rapidly changing and technologically advanced GAI context based literature.

1: Inclusion & Exclusion Criteria

The Ethics of Artificial Intelligence creativity examining challenges and prospects is considered as identified issue. Appraising/ reviewing stage including screening, retrieval and assessment of selected research articles is conducted by following **Two Strategy Designs** including **PRISMA** (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) **flow diagram technique** associated with **Themes based Clusters/ selection criteria** in this study. This technique enables the assessment of research articles on the basis of inclusion of researches where evidence-based minimum set of items are considered for evaluation in systematic reviews. In this study, data is collected and evaluated by PRISMA systematic strategy for scrutiny following recognized steps along with employing another strategy of theme based search. Stated techniques are employed with the view to observe and measure authenticity and generate truth about potential ethical and legal harm or challenges in AI Creativity. It is pertinent to

mention that all the research inquiries were guided by formulated research questions and objectives of the research. Inclusion and exclusion criteria contain following stages:

- 1.1: Identification Stage
- 1.2: Screening Stage
- 1.3: Inclusion Stage

A: Search Strategy Design (based on PRISMA Model)

B: Research Design for Data Extraction Strategy (Selection Criteria based on Identified Thematic Clusters)

1.1: Identification Stage

a) Literature/ Record/ Data identification from Sources/ Databases

This study consists on identification stage including a host of databases as sources for collection of data or records. The employed strategy in this research at identification stage includes 10 or more Scholarly Research/ entertainment/ Social/ Recreational, educational databases (some notables are: Research Rabbit, J store, Google Scholar, Research Gate, WOS, Sage, Springer, Elsevier, YouTube, Facebook, Journal of Applied Artificial Intelligence and Journal of Advanced Engineering, technology & Science) for selection, screening, retrieval and assessment of literature in stated domain. Total 190 studies were identified at first stage. The literature search was started by using keywords “Ethics of Artificial Intelligence”, “Ethical Standards of AI”, “Ethical Framework for Artificial Intelligence”, “Ethical Dilemma of Artificial Intelligence”, “Challenges and Prospects of AI”, “Ethical & Legal Implications in AI”, “Artificial Intelligence Creativity & Copyright Protection” and “Potential Risks & Benefits of AI Creativity”. Finding initial relevancy, each manuscript was determined by its title. From the title, if content seemed to describe the context of stated keywords, its full reference is tried to be obtained including author, year, title and abstract for further evaluation and detailed assessment. Publication dates of literature were also limited to 2016-2024 (Articles published, Videos, entertainment, educational lectures/ programs recorded and posted in the past ten years) are considered eligible so that this study can be structured on recent data/ literature.

b) Reasons of Removal Before Screening

On identification stage, 19 studies were considered as duplicate records which were removed from the search list while 37 searches were removed from the list out of which 21 were marked as ineligible for screening due to indirect connectedness with stated study such as several studies were found from the computing or computer sciences or information technologies domain containing data related to program developing formulas etc. Other 17 studies were removed due to not exact relevancy with themes

of the stated study. Total 133 studies were selected for screening or identified at this stage after careful scrutiny.

1.2: Screening Stage (Screening of Titles & Abstracts)

In order to conduct this study, screening stage includes examining of research studies identified eligible for screening after following careful recruitment strategy by PRISMA flow chart and Themes based Selection. The total number of screened articles were 133 (Title & Abstracts were screened) related to stated study while the 118 studies (Including Research articles, thesis & reports) identified and considered more relevant out of 133 such scholarly studies listed for screening. Out of 133, total 38 studies were excluded. 13 studies were excluded due to unavailability of complete PDF and other accessible files and around 25 studies could not be retrieved due to paid versions of databases. Data has also been screened and extracted according to main highlighted themes. All identified themes were also enlisted and aligned after screening identified or recruited data. Mainly open access journals were tried to access for searching data and another reviewer also appraised the identified matched studies for establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria.

1.3: Inclusion Stage

The quality of literature review is highly dependent on the literature included for the review following “Garbage-in, Garbage-Out” strategy (Bhimani et al., 2019). This stage included studies having relevancy with Ethics of Artificial Intelligence determining challenges and prospects of rapid technological advancement. After formal screening (Titles, Abstracts, Authors, Year, Volume, Full Text/ Reports) of total identified studies 95 (Ninety Five) Literature were included for detailed examination or review. This research study “The Ethics of AI Creativity: Emerging Challenges and Prospects” includes 7 themes identified after studying relevant preliminary literature. This study also included studies written in English, excluding studies in other languages.

Table 1 (Inclusion & Exclusion Criteria)

Included articles	Excluded articles
Full-text was available	Full text was not available
Previous Studies for Historical Evolution References	Computational Irrelevant
Historical Studies	
Published in the period between 2016 and 2024 timeframe	Outside the search
English written articles	Non-English articles
In the domain of GAI research questions	Were not related to the
Related to the research questions	Were duplicated studies

2: Quality Assessment/Full-Text Assessment

This is the stage for formulating the pool of studies for data extraction and synthesis. To assess the quality of every selected review paper by using pre-set criteria (Kitchenham, 2007). Full-text assessment or systematic literature review is considered essential requirement in any academic research where knowledge advancement is needed to be established on previous studies. Previous studies on Ethics of AI examining potential challenges and prospects provide strong grounds in structuring novel philosophical perceptions based on existing scientific evidences. It was tried to conduct a quality assessment of this review as a means of evaluating the quality accuracy of selected papers.

In process of reviewing literature related to Ethical standards of Artificial Intelligence particularly digging emerging challenges and prospects of this technological advancement, it expanded the scope and depth of the existing structure of studies based on ethical considerations for Artificial Intelligence and also identified gaps for further exploration. Considering full-text assessment of each or individual existing identified, screened literature by summarizing, analyzing considerations towards ethical and legal dilemma were also carefully synthesized. The validity and quality of existing work was also tried to be evaluated through this systematic literature review under 7 thematic clusters. Quality assessment is the way to explore weaknesses, inconsistencies and contradictions in studies (Ahmed et al., 2019). Following criteria was developed for this review to assess the quality and accuracy of papers reviewed in this study:

- 1: Is each study addressed the question of ethical considerations, challenges and prospects of Artificial Intelligence?
- 2: Are the objectives of each study matched with questions under consideration?
- 3: Is the context was clear in which the study was carried out?
- 4: Is the research Methodology appropriately applied and described to identify related issues in each study?
- 5: Is the process of data collection and data analysis approach clearly explained and evaluated in each study?

The five quality assessment questions were listed to evaluate the 95 research papers. This way is helpful in strengthening the researcher’s confidence in the credibility of findings (Ahmed et al., 2019).

3: Data Extraction Criteria

Data extraction is the most significant activities in the SLR Procedure. The primary objective of this part is to table or enlist highlighted data in order to accurately recording the assembled information through the comprehensive review (Kitchenham et al., 2009). Extraction on the basis of further classification of methodological approaches, objectives, variables, findings scrutiny include thematic synthesis, conclusions and generalizations are made based on the themes (Ahmed et al., 2019) and concepts that are coded or tabled according to planned recognized strategy. In this study, Record/Data is being extracted from enlisted studies and grouped according to thematic clusters. After a careful scrutiny of record’s selection, followed by PRISMA flow diagram for inclusion and exclusion criteria. Identification, screening and selection criteria contains complete

description of reasons for inclusion and exclusion (Bhimani et al., 2019).

This process was carried out by scanning every individual selected study, and extracting required related data was being highlighted according to pre-set seven main thematic clusters and under elements of systematic sampling criteria tabled in columns of

Serial.no, paper title, publication year, type of paper, Methodological approaches, theoretical frameworks and major findings of studies. The table 2 contains essential categorization of data extraction and systematic sampling details are attached in Annexure 1.

Table 2 Data extraction / Systematic Sampling Criteria

Extracted Data	Description
SNO	Serial Numbers for each Paper
Authors	Names of all the authors
Publication Year	Paper publishing Year
Study Title	The name of the paper, appearing in the searching stage
Type of Paper	Book Chapter, Journal, Conference, workshop article
Methodology	Details of used methodological Approaches
Theory to conduct study	Details of theoretical models/ Frameworks adopted
Major Findings/ Conclusion of the studies.	Description of the overall findings/ conclusions of

Detailed Systematic Sampling Table is attached in Annexure A

4: Data Analysis & Synthesis

All articles are summarized in separate draft with highlighting methodological approaches, objectives and findings of every individual study. Such separated highlighted articles were further tabled according to pre-specified themes or clusters with systematic descriptions. In this review, the research topic is considered primary concern of exploration or examination with content that has been comprehensively examined and sightseen (Ahmed et al., 2019). Analysis of selected studies revealed comprehensive overview on the stated area within pre-arranged extraction criteria and identified six thematic clusters, which include Societal Impact, economic inequality, Human autonomy, innovation, operational, implementation challenges, Copyright protection and regulation and interdisciplinary Integration including alignment of the Values of Systems with Human Values (Ethical aspects). The five quality assessment listed questions to evaluate the 95 selected record were also considered at data analysis and synthesis phase.

During data analysis and synthesis phase, it has been analyzed through pre-set criteria that methodological applications and theoretical lenses used in mostly selected studies are comprehensive analysis and review methodology. Reviewed studies contained a range of theories and models applied to determine the ideal ethical framework for AI considering emerging challenges and prospects. After comprehensive review of selected record, similar content extracted from studies was categorized into specified 6 thematic clusters raising need of ethical governance and considerations are necessary to be formulated.

Findings

The examined studies recommend more inclusive deliberative procedures and better integration of philosophical expertise in AI ethics. Based on comprehensive systematic review of extracted records, findings are enumerated in following thematic manner:

Societal Challenges

i) Social choice manipulations in AI systems, distinguishing between design and implementation stages

- ii) Social-systems analysis to assess AI's long-term societal impacts
- iii) Privacy concerns and protection of user data.
- iv) Accountability for AI systems' actions and decisions.
- v) Fairness and avoiding unfair biases or discrimination.
- vi) Potential for manipulation, such as political manipulation of voters.
- vii) Threats to human life, liberty, and security.
- viii) Challenges to human dignity.
- ix) Unintended consequences of AI for Good initiatives.
- x) Surveillance capitalism and data harvesting without proper consent.
- xi) Impacts on mental health
- xii) Disproportionate effects on disadvantaged groups

Economic Inequality

- i) Unemployment concerns and inequality as AI replaces human workers.
- ii) "Reward hacking" where AI finds unintended ways to maximize rewards.

Human Autonomy

- i) Developing disciplines to make AI human-centric and codifying AI ethics categories.
- ii) Difficulty in adhering to human-centered values during AI development
- iii) The biased nature of humans influencing AI systems.
- iv) AI's lack of human emotions and potential negative side effects.
- v) Preserving human autonomy as AI becomes more integral to decision-making.
- vi) Importance of human input and vigilance in AI systems.

Innovation, Operational & Implementation Challenges & Prospects

- i) Lack of tools for effective communication between AI developers and data collectors.
- ii) Issues with data quality and collection processes
- iii) Importance of developing high-quality labeled data to train ethical AI systems.

- iv) Developing legitimate processes for decisions about AI development and use.
- v) Developing systems to evaluate
- vi) AI judgment quality and implementing emergency stop mechanisms for autonomous systems.
- vii) Improving data quality and AI training processes to enhance ethical outcomes.
- viii) Technology firms are urged to promote socially advantageous uses of AI while discouraging potentially negative applications.

Copyright Protection/ Regulation

- i) Academic misconduct, plagiarism, and challenges in detecting AI-generated text.
- ii) Issues of authorship, copyright, and accountability in academic settings.
- iii) Prioritizing international coordination in AI governance to prevent fragmented regulatory landscapes.
- iv) Developing methodologies for evaluating AI-generated text reliability and addressing associated legal challenges.
- v) Digital technologies have made unauthorized reproduction and distribution of copyrighted works easier.
- vi) There are jurisdictional issues with enforcing copyrights across borders online.
- vii) Balancing copyright holders' rights with public access to information is challenging.
- viii) Copyright laws need to adapt to new technologies and digital works
- ix) Develop technical protection measures like encryption and watermarking.
- x) Update laws and treaties to cover new digital works and uses.
- xi) Create online dispute resolution mechanisms for cross-border issues.
- xii) Explore new business models balancing access and compensation.
- xiii) Increase public education on digital copyright.
- xiv) Adopt a multifaceted approach combining legal, technological and economic solutions

Interdisciplinary Integration to Practical Implementation

- i) Explainable AI (XAI) techniques are being developed to increase transparency and build trust in AI systems.
- ii) Developing disciplines to make AI human-centric and codifying AI ethics categories.
- iii) Limited awareness and understanding of AI ethics among practitioners.
- iv) Technology firms are urged to promote socially advantageous uses of AI while discouraging potentially negative applications.
- v) Incorporating AI critique and evaluation into classroom learning to foster critical digital literacy.
- vi) Enhancing cross-disciplinary collaboration between philosophers, AI researchers, and experts from other fields to address complex ethical issues.

The **Ethical Framework** for AI identified in the documents focuses on principles of fairness, transparency, accountability, privacy, security, reliability, safety, and human-centered values.

Privacy & Data Protection

Safeguarding informational privacy and addressing new data protection risks created by AI capabilities is essential. AI's reliance on vast amounts of personal data raises concerns about surveillance, profiling, and infringement of privacy rights.

Accountability & Professional Responsibility

Accountability and responsibility are essential ethical standards, with the need to establish clear lines of accountability for AI decisions and actions. This includes developing flexible and adaptive governance structures to address the complex and evolving ethical challenges of AI. Determining liability and responsibility when AI systems cause harm, especially in autonomous decision-making scenarios.

Safety & Security

Regulatory frameworks need to evolve to accommodate AI technologies while ensuring safety and effectiveness.

Transparency & Explainability

The opacity and unpredictability of some AI systems raise concerns about understanding and explaining their decisions. Lack of transparency in AI systems makes it difficult to understand decision-making processes and raising accountability concerns. Promoting transparency in AI use and encouraging proper acknowledgment of AI-generated information.

Fairness, Non-discrimination & Mitigation of Biasness

AI systems can perpetuate and amplify societal biases, leading to discriminatory outcomes. Ensuring equality and non-discrimination is a key ethical standard, as machine learning systems can inadvertently reproduce or amplify existing biases. This includes protecting fundamental human rights and preventing AI from infringing on the right to equality.

Human Control of Technology / Promotion of Human Values

Human flourishing/ Human well-being is proposed as an overarching ethical framework for evaluating and guiding AI development and deployment

Discussion

The premature adoption of unbridled AI made it necessary to philosophically explore the consequences of this driverless technology. Similarly the creative addition of AI increases the high risks to Intellectual Property rights of any individual or entity and it becomes inevitable to take concrete measures. Coping up with the challenges and the ethical dilemmas, systematic literary considerations are employed to generally formulate an ethical guideline with careful analysis and extensive review of studies. Several aspects are considered for exploration of AI Ethical standards with examining the challenges or risk compromising such ethical standards in AI.

This study employs an effort to ascertain the creative aspects of machine as well as human mind by analyzing ethical challenges and prospects of AI through the systematic literature review using PRISMA Model. The study provides a comprehensive systematic review of literature forming a ground for analyzing the need of responsive and adaptive policies ensuring more responsive creative and ethical

measures to the challenges posed by AI in media landscape. Systematic literature review helps in minimizing biasness and maximizing the contribution of empirical studies in formulating opinions to take concrete measures regarding ethical aspects of AI including challenges and future prospects.

As it is obvious that AI systems interacting with the physical world, therefore the need to establish clear lines of accountability for AI decisions and actions are considered imperative. In order to address the complex and evolving ethical challenges of AI, developing flexible and adaptive governance structures is emphasized through this systematic study.

Several ethical standards and frameworks for AI are identified across multiple papers. Ethical assessment contains comprehensive analysis suggesting direct and indirect ethical dimensions.

The research findings highlight the complex ethical landscape surrounding artificial intelligence, revealing numerous challenges and prospects that require careful consideration. One of the primary concerns is the potential for AI systems to perpetuate and amplify societal biases, leading to discriminatory outcomes in areas such as hiring and law enforcement. This underscores the critical need for ensuring fairness and non-discrimination in AI development and deployment. Privacy and data protection emerge as significant issues, particularly in the context of surveillance capitalism. The vast amounts of personal data required by AI systems raise concerns about profiling and infringement of privacy rights. Addressing these concerns is essential for maintaining public trust in AI technologies.

Transparency and explainability of AI systems are identified as crucial ethical standards. The opacity of some AI systems makes it challenging to understand and explain their decisions, which can lead to accountability issues. This highlights the need for developing techniques to make AI systems more interpretable and their decision-making processes more transparent.

The research also emphasizes the importance of human control over technology and the promotion of human values. There is a growing recognition that AI development and deployment should be guided by an overarching ethical framework centered on human flourishing and well-being. This aligns with the need

for inclusive deliberative procedures and better integration of philosophical expertise in AI ethics discussions.

To address these challenges, the research proposes several strategies. These include implementing robust ethical frameworks focusing on fairness, transparency, and accountability. Cross-disciplinary collaboration between philosophers, AI researchers, and experts from other fields is recommended to address complex ethical issues. Continuous monitoring and testing of AI systems for biases and unintended consequences are also suggested. The study also highlights the need for adaptive governance structures to address the evolving ethical challenges of AI. This includes developing clear guidelines and ethical standards for using AI in various sectors, such as education. Furthermore, the research emphasizes the importance of balancing the benefits of AI against potential risks and ensuring a fair distribution of these benefits.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the ethical considerations surrounding AI are multifaceted and require ongoing attention from researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. By addressing these challenges and leveraging the prospects identified in the research, we can work towards responsible AI deployment that aligns with human values and societal norms. According to the systematic literature review, the ethical challenges and prospects of AI present a complex picture that requires multifaceted approaches. The research concludes that addressing issues of bias, transparency and accountability is crucial to building trust in AI technologies. It is essential to develop comprehensive ethical frameworks and global standards, with a focus on principles such as equity, privacy, security and human-centered values. The study emphasizes the need for interdisciplinary collaboration between philosophers, AI researchers and experts from various fields to address complex ethical issues. Continuous monitoring and testing of AI systems to detect biases and unintended consequences is recommended, along with the development of explainable AI techniques to increase transparency. The research also highlights the importance of balancing innovation with ethical standards, ensuring that AI development aligns with societal values while encouraging technological advancement.

Furthermore, the study highlights the need for inclusive deliberative procedures and better integration of philosophical expertise in AI ethics debates. In conclusion, ethical considerations of AI require continued vigilance, adaptive governance structures, and a commitment to human-centered values to ensure responsible deployment of AI that serves the public good.

References:

- 28(4), 689–707. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-018-9482-5>
- Abbas, A. (n.d.). *AI in Healthcare: Applications, Challenges, and Future Prospects*.
- Ahmed, Y. A., Ahmad, M. N., Ahmad, N., & Zakaria, N. H. (2019). Social media for knowledge-sharing: A systematic literature review. *Telematics and Informatics*, 37, 72–112.
- AlAli, R., & Wardat, Y. (2024). Opportunities and challenges of integrating generative artificial intelligence in education. *International Journal of Religion*, 5(7), 784–793.
- Ashok, M., Madan, R., Joha, A., & Sivarajah, U. (2022). Ethical framework for Artificial Intelligence and Digital technologies. *International Journal of Information Management*, 62, 102433.
- Babajide Tolulope Familoni. (2024). Ethical frameworks for AI in healthcare entrepreneurship: A theoretical examination of challenges and approaches. *International Journal of Frontiers in Biology and Pharmacy Research*, 5(1), 057–065. <https://doi.org/10.53294/ijfbpr.2024.5.1.0032>
- Bhimani, H., Mention, A.-L., & Barlatier, P.-J. (2019). Social media and innovation: A systematic literature review and future research directions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 144, 251–269.
- Boddington, P. (2017). *Towards a Code of Ethics for Artificial Intelligence*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60648-4>
- Calo, R. (2017). Artificial intelligence policy: A primer and roadmap. *UCDL Rev.*, 51, 399.
- Cappelli, M. A., & Di Marzo Serugendo, G. (2024). A semi-automated software model to support AI ethics compliance assessment of an AI system guided by ethical principles of AI. *AI and Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-024-00480-z>
- Cath, C. (2018). Governing artificial intelligence: Ethical, legal and technical opportunities and challenges. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 376(2133), 20180080. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2018.0080>
- Christin, A. (2017). Algorithms in practice: Comparing web journalism and criminal justice. *Big Data & Society*, 4(2), 205395171771885. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951717718855>
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Hughes, L., Ismagilova, E., Aarts, G., Coombs, C., Crick, T., Duan, Y., Dwivedi, R., Edwards, J., & Eirug, A. (2021). Artificial Intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary perspectives on emerging challenges, opportunities, and agenda for research, practice and policy. *International Journal of Information Management*, 57, 101994.
- Fjeld, J., Achten, N., Hilligoss, H., Nagy, A., & Srikumar, M. (2020). Principled artificial intelligence: Mapping consensus in ethical and rights-based approaches to principles for AI. *Berkman Klein Center Research Publication*, 2020–1. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3518482
- Floridi, L., & Cowls, J. (2022). A Unified Framework of Five Principles for AI in Society. In S. Carta (Ed.), *Machine Learning and the City* (1st ed., pp. 535–545). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119815075.ch45>
- Floridi, L., Cowls, J., Beltrametti, M., Chatila, R., Chazerand, P., Dignum, V., Luetge, C., Madelin, R., for a Good AI Society: Opportunities, Risks, Principles, and Recommendations. *Minds and Machines*,

- Fraga-Lamas, P., & Fernandez-Carames, T. M. (2020). Fake news, disinformation, and deepfakes: Leveraging distributed ledger technologies and blockchain to combat digital deception and counterfeit reality. *IT Professional*, 22(2), 53–59.
- Gao, D. K., Haverly, A., Mittal, S., Wu, J., & Chen, J. (2024). AI Ethics: A Bibliometric Analysis, Critical Issues, and Key Gaps. *International Journal of Business Analytics (IJBAN)*, 11(1), 1–19.
- Garon, J. (2023). A Practical Introduction to Generative AI, Synthetic Media, and the Messages Found in the Latest Medium. *Synthetic Media, and the Messages Found in the Latest Medium (March 14, 2023)*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4388437
- Garon, J. M. (2023). *The Revolution Will Be Digitized: Generative AI, Synthetic Media, and the Medium of Disruption*. <https://kb.osu.edu/bitstreams/65023bfa-9388-439f-bf47-7b8eb6d2c849/download>
- Gerke, S., Minssen, T., & Cohen, G. (2020). Ethical and legal challenges of artificial intelligence-driven healthcare. In *Artificial intelligence in healthcare* (pp. 295–336). Elsevier. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128184387000125>
- Ghose, A., Ali, S. A., & Mishra, A. M. (2024). Artistic expressions, generative AI, and legal tapestry: Exploring the dynamics of Copyright laws in the confluence of AI and artistic creation. In *Making Art with Generative AI Tools* (pp. 198–214). IGI Global. <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/artistic-expressions-generative-ai-and-legal-tapestry/343429>
- Greene, D., Hoffmann, A. L., & Stark, L. (2019). *Better, nicer, clearer, fairer: A critical assessment of the movement for ethical artificial intelligence and machine learning*. https://aisel.aisnet.org/hicss-52/dsm/critical_and_ethical_studies/2/
- He, V. F., Shrestha, Y. R., Puranam, P., & Miron-Spektor, E. (2023). *Searching Together: A Theory of Human-AI Co-Creativity*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4603650
- Holstein, K., Wortman Vaughan, J., Daumé, H., Dudik, M., & Wallach, H. (2019). Improving Fairness in Machine Learning Systems: What Do Industry Practitioners Need? *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300830>
- Innes, M., Dobрева, D., & Innes, H. (2021). Disinformation and digital influencing after terrorism: Spoofing, truthing and social proofing. *Contemporary Social Science*, 16(2), 241–255. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21582041.2019.1569714>
- Jedličková, A. (2024). Ethical approaches in designing autonomous and intelligent systems: A comprehensive survey towards responsible development. *AI & SOCIETY*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-024-02040-9>
- Kandel, N. (2020). Information disorder syndrome and its management. *JNMA: Journal of the Nepal Medical Association*, 58(224), 280.
- Kazim, E., & Koshiyama, A. S. (2021). A high-level overview of AI ethics. *Patterns*, 2(9). [https://www.cell.com/patterns/pdf/S2666-3899\(21\)00157-4.pdf](https://www.cell.com/patterns/pdf/S2666-3899(21)00157-4.pdf)
- Khan, T., Michalas, A., & Akhunzada, A. (2021). Fake news outbreak 2021: Can we stop the viral spread? *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 190, 103112.
- Kitchenham, B., Brereton, O. P., Budgen, D., Turner, M., Bailey, J., & Linkman, S. (2009). Systematic
- Langraw, K. S., & Zaman, A. (2023). A Study on Evaluating the Impact of Social Media's Fake News on The Attitudes and Beliefs of a Society. *International Journal of Social Science & Entrepreneurship*, 3(4), 254–270.
- Leslie, D. (2019). *Understanding artificial intelligence ethics and safety*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3240529>

- Lewis, D., & Moorkens, J. (2020). A Rights-Based Approach to Trustworthy AI in Social Media. *Social Media + Society*, 6(3), 205630512095467. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305120954672>
- literature reviews in software engineering—a systematic literature review. *Information and Software*
- Mammen, C. E., & Richey, C. (2020). AI and IP: Are Creativity and Inventorship Inherently Human Activities? *FIU L. Rev.*, 14, 275.
- McCormack, J., Hutchings, P., Gifford, T., Yee-King, M., Llano, M. T., & D'inverno, M. (2020). Design considerations for real-time collaboration with creative artificial intelligence. *Organised Sound*, 25(1), 41–52.
- Pagallo, U., Rossi, F., Schafer, B., Valcke, P., & Vayena, E. (2018). AI4People—An Ethical Framework *Technology*, 51(1), 7–15.
- Mensah, G. B. (n.d.). *Ethics, Bias, and Risks in AI diagnosis*. Retrieved September 26, 2024, from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/George-Benneh-Mensah/publication/381584371_Ethics_Bias_and_Risks_in_AI_diagnosis/links/667550f11dec0c3c6f986b17/Ethics-Bias-and-Risks-in-AI-diagnosis.pdf
- Mitchell, M. (2018). Comment on —The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Innovation: An Exploratory Analysis. In *The Economics of Artificial Intelligence: An Agenda* (pp. 146–148). University of Chicago Press. <https://www.nber.org/books-and-chapters/economics-artificial-intelligence-agenda/comment-impact-artificial-intelligence-innovation-exploratory-analysis-mitchell>
- Mogol, N., & Crudu, R. (2022). Challenges and strategies for copyright protection in the digital era. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 4, 6–19.
- Naqvi, Z. (2020). Artificial intelligence, copyright, and copyright infringement. *Marq. Intell. Prop. L. Rev.*, 24, 15.
- Naudts, L. (2019). *Towards a Code of Ethics for Artificial Intelligence*. HeinOnline. https://heinonline.org/hol-cgi-bin/get_pdf.cgi?handle=hein.journals/delphi2§ion=26
- Olorunsogo, T., Adeniyi, A. O., Okolo, C. A., & Babawarun, O. (2024). Ethical considerations in AI-enhanced medical decision support systems: A review. *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*, 11(1), 329–336. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjaets.2024.11.1.0061>
- Orfanidou, A. (n.d.). *Digital Immigrants: Media Literacy Skills and Combating Information Disorder*. Retrieved April 30, 2025, from <https://pjl.jour.auth.gr/index.php/en/news/digital-immigrants-media-literacy-skills-and-combating-information-disorder>
- Pawelec, M. (2022). Deepfakes and Democracy (Theory): How Synthetic Audio-Visual Media for Disinformation and Hate Speech Threaten Core Democratic Functions. *Digital Society*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44206-022-00010-6>
- Powers, T. M., & Ganascia, J.-G. (2020). The Ethics of the Ethics of AI. *The Oxford Handbook of Ethics of AI*, 25–51.
- Raj, R., & Kos, A. (2022). A comprehensive study of mobile robot: History, developments, applications, and future research perspectives. *Applied Sciences*, 12(14), 6951.
- Roitblat, H. L. (2020). *Algorithms Are Not Enough: Creating General Artificial Intelligence*. MIT Press.
- Saini, M. K., & Kumar, A. (2020). AI in Healthcare: Applications, Challenges, and Future Prospects. *RES MILITARIS*, 10(1), 141–148.
- Sandiumenge, I. (2023). Copyright Implications of the Use of Generative AI. Available at SSRN 4531912. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4531912

- Serrano-Puche, J. (2021). Digital disinformation and emotions: Exploring the social risks of affective polarization. *International Review of Sociology*, 31(2), 231–245. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03906701.2021.1947953>
- Shaw, J., Rudzicz, F., Jamieson, T., & Goldfarb, A. (2019). Artificial intelligence and the implementation challenge. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 21(7), e13659.
- Singh, K. (2024). *AI and Healthcare: Opportunities and Challenges*. <http://archive.article4submit.com/id/eprint/2773/>
- Stahl, B. C. (2021). *Artificial intelligence for a better future: An ecosystem perspective on the ethics of AI and emerging digital technologies*. Springer Nature. <https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/48228>
- Tolulope Olorunsogo, Adekunle Oyeyemi Adeniyi, Chioma Anthonia Okolo, & Oloruntoba Babawarun. (2024). Ethical considerations in AI-enhanced medical decision support systems: A review. *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*, 11(1), 329–336. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjaets.2024.11.1.0061>
- Veale, M., & Binns, R. (2017). Fairer machine learning in the real world: Mitigating discrimination without collecting sensitive data. *Big Data & Society*, 4(2), 205395171774353. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951717743530>
- Villaronga, E. F., Kieseberg, P., & Li, T. (2018). Humans forget, machines remember: Artificial intelligence and the right to be forgotten. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 34(2), 304–313.
- Wach, K., Duong, C. D., Ejdy, J., Kazlauskaitė, R., Korzynski, P., Mazurek, G., Paliszkiwicz, J., & Ziemba, E. (2023). The dark side of generative artificial intelligence: A critical analysis of controversies and risks of ChatGPT. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 11(2), 7–30.
- Wagner, B. (2019). Ethics As An Escape From Regulation. From —Ethics-Washing To Ethics-Shopping? In E. Bayamlioglu, I. Baraliuc, L. A. W. Janssens, & M. Hildebrandt (Eds.), *BEING PROFILED* (pp. 84–89). Amsterdam University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9789048550180-016>
- Wardle, C. (2018). Information disorder: The essential glossary. Harvard, MA: Shorenstein Center on Media, Politics, and Public Policy, Harvard Kennedy School. https://www.globacademy.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/infoDisorder_glossary.pdf
- Winfield, A. F. T., & Jirotko, M. (2018). Ethical governance is essential to building trust in robotics and artificial intelligence systems. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 376(2133), 20180085. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2018.0085>
- Yang, H. (2025). Artificial intelligence art robots: The future of technological art or the end of the human artist? *International Theory and Practice in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 243–251.
- Yuan, X., He, P., Zhu, Q., & Li, X. (2019). Adversarial examples: Attacks and defenses for deep learning. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 30(9), 2805–2824.
- Zakir, S., Bareach, N.-D., Alam, R., & Farman, S. (2022). “Ethical Values & Reasonable Restriction In Freedom Of Speech And Expression”“A Study Of Examining Ethical And Legal Journalism Practices In Balochistan”. *Webology*, 19(2).

- Zakir, S., Bibi, S., Butt, D., Gul, R., & Khan, N. (2025). GAI Creative Content in Media and Education: Is Human-AI Co-Creativity Worthy of Copyright Protection? *Review Journal of Social Psychology & Social Works*, 3(2), 606-619.
- Zirpoli, C. T. (2023). *Generative Artificial Intelligence and Copyright Law*. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/scholcom/243/>
- Zurth, P. (2020). Artificial Creativity? A Case Against Copyright Protection for AI-Generated Works. *UCLA JL & Tech.*, 25, i.
- Ahmad, I., & Gul, R. (2023). Service-Learning and Vocational Education. *Service-Learning: Theory and Practice*. Taylor & Francis.
- Ahmad, I., & Gul, R. (2023). Service-Learning Models. *Service-Learning: Theory and Practice*. Taylor & Francis.
- Ali, S., Gul, R., & Gul, U. (2025). Perceptions of teachers on practicing personal values in their teaching at secondary school level. *Review Journal of Social Psychology & Social Works*, 2(2), 324-330.
- Ayub, A., Gul, R., Ali, A., & Rauf, B. M. (2021). Cultural and educational stress: A case study of Brahui speaking ESL and EMI periphery students. *Asian EFL Journal*, 28(2.3), 123-145.
- Bareach, N.-u.-D., & Gul, R. (2025). Legal framework regulating the old age homes: An analysis of challenges faced by elderly for legislative reforms in Pakistan. *Social Science Review Archives*, 3(1), 2470-2475.
- Bukhari, S. K. U. S., Gul, R., Bashir, T., Zakir, S., & Javed, T. (2021). Exploring managerial skills of Pakistan public universities' middle managers for campus sustainability. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 11(3), 1-19.
- Gul, R. (2023). Relationship Between Self-Concept and Academic Achievement: An Evidence of Female Students. *Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 11(1), 100-115.
- Gul, R., & Ahmad, I. (2022). A Qualitative Inquiry of University Students' Experiences of Exam Stress and Its Effect on Their Academic Performance. *Human Arenas*, 5(3), 250-265.
- Gul, R., & Ahmad, I. (2022). A Qualitative Study of Workplace Factors Causing Stress Among University Teachers and Coping Strategies. *Human Arenas*, 5(2), 200-215.
- Gul, R., & Ahmad, I. (2023). Understanding the Pedagogical Role of Service-Learning for Preparing Citizen Leaders in Higher Education. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 10(2), 45-60.
- Gul, R., & Ali, I. (2021). An Evaluative Study of English Contrastive Rhetoric in Pashtu Speaking Areas of Pakistan: A Case Study of District Swat. *Linguistica Antverpiensia*, 2021(2), 2184-2199.
- Gul, R., & Ali, I. (2021). The Impact of Education on Business Opportunities for Women Entrepreneurs in Public & Private Television Advertisements in Pakistan. *Industrial Engineering & Management Systems*, 20(2), 140-147.
- Gul, R., & Dogar, A. A. (2021). Effectiveness of Continuous Professional Development Program as Perceived by Primary Level Teachers. *Journal of Educational Research*, 24(1), 80-95.
- Gul, R., & Khan, S. S. (2020). Organizational Politics as Antecedent of Stress in Public Sector Universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 9(2), 150-165.
- Gul, R., & Khan, S. S. (2021). Influence of Logical and Spatial Intelligence on Teaching Pedagogies of Secondary School Teachers. *Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews*, 8(6), 1-9.
- Gul, R., & Khilji, G. (2021). Exploring the need for a responsive school curriculum to cope with the Covid-19 pandemic in Pakistan. *Prospects*, 51(1), 1-14. [SpringerLink](#)

- Gul, R., & Reba, A. (2022). An Investigation into the Teachers' Intelligences on Their Teaching Strategies at Secondary Level in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province of Pakistan. *Journal of Educational Research*, 25(1), 50-65.
- Gul, R., & Tahir, T. (2023). Impact of Teachers' Workload on Their Time Management Skills at University Level. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 3(1), 322-334.
- Gul, R., & Tahir, T. (2023). Perspectives of the Teachers on Challenges and Possibilities to Online System of Education Amid COVID-19 Outbreak in Balochistan, Pakistan. *SAGE Open*, 13(1), 21582440231155063.
- Gul, R., Ayub, A., Mazhar, S., Uddin, S. S., & Khanum, M. (2021). Teachers' perceptions on students' cultural and linguistic diversity and its impact on their approaches towards culturally teaching practices. *TESOL International Journal*, 16(3.2), 95-110. [Academia](#)
- Gul, R., Kanwal, S., & Khan, S. S. (2020). Preferences of the teachers in employing revised Bloom's taxonomy in their instructions. *Sir Syed Journal of Education & Social Research*, 3(2), 258-266.
- Gul, R., Rabbi, F., Batool, S., Tahir, T., & Asif, M. (2024). Exploring gender disparities related challenges in competencies for sustainable development at higher educational institutions in Pakistan. *Evolutionary Studies in Imaginative Culture*, 8(2), 1585-1591.
- Gul, R., Talat, M., Mumtaz, M., & Shaheen, L. (2021). Does intelligence matter in teaching? Exploring the impact of teachers' intelligence on teaching pedagogies of secondary school science teachers. *Multicultural Education*, 7(3), 45-58.
- Khan, J. A., Gul, R., Riaz, T., Bibi, S., & Ahmad, S. (2025). Pre-service teachers' perceptions of supervisor feedback: Evaluating the effectiveness of teaching practicum support in Pakistan. *Review Journal of Social Psychology and Social Work*, 3(1).
- Sohail, M., Gul, R., & Mushtaq, R. (2018). The establishment of Azad School Utmanzai and Anjuman-i-Islahul Afaghina: A successful methodology of organizational excellence (1921-1946). *Global Social Sciences Review*, 3(3), 193-206.
- Tufail, G. M., Gul, R., & Ali, H. (2024). Humble leadership and knowledge hiding: Mediating role of psychological empowerment. *Journal of Business & Economics*, 15(1), 50-65.
- Gul, K., Ilyas, M., Gul, R., Riaz, T., & Khan, A. M. (2025). Investigating the prevalence of depression and anxiety in burnt patients: A cross-sectional study in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Physical Education Health and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 208-217.
- Gul, R., Alm, A., Ayub, A., Saleem, T., & Mahmood, N. (2024). The role of institutional support in sustainable development competencies among academic faculty at higher educational institutions. *Kurdish Studies*, 12(5), 1692-1896.
- Gul, R., Rabbi, F., Batool, S., Tahir, T., & Asif, M. (2024). Exploring gender disparities related challenges in competencies for sustainable development at higher education institutions in Pakistan. *Evolutionary Studies in Imaginative Culture*, 8(2 Suppl.), 1585-1591.
- Mehmood, S., Rao, S. N., & Gul, R. (2024). Impact of psychological contract violation on turnover intentions among project employees: Mediating role of burnout and moderating role of self-efficacy. *Journal of Business and Tourism*, 10(1), 62-78.
- Rabbi, F., & Gul, R. (2023). Students' knowledge of metacognitive strategies and use of technology in their writing skills. *International Journal of Social Science Archives*, 19(2), 25-39.
- Tufail, M., Gul, R., & Ali, H. (2024). Humble leadership and knowledge hiding: Mediating role of psychological empowerment. *Journal of Business & Economics*, 16(1), 102-115.